

Horizon Europe

Project 101059188

Briefing Paper 10

Methodological protocol: visual elicitation interviews with tenants and landlords based on housing-history drawings and photos of home

Action The affective economies of emerging private renting markets: understanding tenants and landlords in postcommunist Romania (AFFECTIVE-PRS)

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Version 1.0

5 May 2025

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Contents

1. PROJECT SUMMARY	4
2. AIM OF THIS BRIEFING PAPER	4
3. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	4
4. VISUALS: PARTICIPANT INSTRUCTIONS	5
Photographs of home	5
My housing journey (hand-drawn sketch)	6
5. INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	11
Summary	11
Warming-up	12
Visual elicitation (part 1)	12
Housing history (in-depth visual elicitation)	12
Photos of home (brief discussion)	12
The rented property/home (part 2)	13
The private renting system (part 3)	14
Debriefing	15
6. RESULTING DATA	15

Figures

Figure 1 My housing history in the form of a list with circles	7
Figure 2 My Housing history in the form of a road and an image of the area	8
Figure 3 My housing history in the form of a list and the floor plan of the home	9
Figure 4 My housing history in the form of a road and the façade of the home	10

1. PROJECT SUMMARY

The 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic and its aftermath have exposed rental housing as a mechanism that generates significant inequalities in wealth, health, and wellbeing in much of the world, while failing to provide many tenants with a sense of home. Academic interest in the Anglo-Saxon countries and the old EU member states has recently contributed disturbing insights (e.g. poor housing quality, insecurity, eviction, economic stress), raising legitimate concerns about tenants' wellbeing in the more hidden, and therefore riskier, private renting sectors (PRS), where informal transactions increase risks and hide vulnerability from the state regulatory gaze.

Sharing these important concerns, the AFFECTIVE-PRS project engages with the renting practices of emerging, 'hidden' PRS, taking as a case-study the post-communist space, specifically Romania. It aims to understand a hidden social world by asking why tenants and landlords engage in the sector, whether their practices allow making a private tenancy home, and how they construct ideas of power, risk, and trust. Methodologically, the project approached tenants and landlords in Romania through an online qualitative questionnaire and online visual elicitation interviews. [This Briefing Paper presents the methodological protocol for the visual-elicitation interviews.](#) For the qualitative questionnaires, please see <https://zenodo.org/records/7566158>¹

2. AIM OF THIS BRIEFING PAPER

This paper presents the methodological protocol and interview outline used in the AFFECTIVE-PRS project. It contributes to making the AFFECTIVE-PRS research approach FAIR, that is, more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable by other academic users. This paper presents:

- ✚ Ethical considerations (Section 3)
- ✚ Information provided to participants regarding the submission of the visuals (Section 4)
- ✚ Interview questions (Section 5)
- ✚ Resulting data (Section 6)

Results and information on data analysis have been reported elsewhere.^{2 3}

3. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Bucharest's Research Ethics Committee, email cometc@unibuc.ro. A Data Management Plan was designed, approved, and followed throughout the entire research process.

Signed informed consent regarding confidentiality/anonymity, specific method clauses (e.g. recording), data usage - [separately for words, photographs, and housing-history drawings](#) - and data storage was obtained from all participants prior to participation. Participants were made aware that visual data poses additional confidentiality/anonymity challenges, increasing the likelihood of them being recognised by people who know them^{4 5} (e.g. photos of landlords' rented properties increase the likelihood of the landlord being recognised by their tenants, and vice versa). These additional ethical considerations regarding visual data do not, however, preclude research on the materialities of home, as prior studies demonstrate, whether its tenure is rented or

¹ Soaita, A. M. (2023). *Qualitative Online Questionnaire: Design Protocol*. University of Bucharest, Briefing Paper 2.

² Soaita, A. M. (2024). "The social vibe of the tenant/landlord relationship in a 'tenant-market': the case of Romania." *Housing Studies*.

³ Soaita, A. M. (2024). "Editorial: For a better private renting system: learning from ignored geographies" *ENHR Newsletter*. City: ENHR, pp. 3-4.

⁴ Guillemin, M., and Drew, S. (2010). "Questions of Process in Participant-Generated Visual Methodologies." *Visual Studies*, 25(2), 175-188.

⁵ Lapenta, F. (2014). "Some theoretical and methodological views on photo-elicitation", in E. Margolis and L. Pauwels, (eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Visual Research Methods*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

owned^{6 7 8 9} or whether it involves more vulnerable groups.^{10 11 12} As is commonly practised, participants were rewarded for their time with a €20 "Thank You" voucher for participation in the interview and an additional one for contributing the housing-history drawing.

Interviews were conducted in Romanian, the native language of participants and of the researcher (myself). They were professionally transcribed (in intelligent verbatim style), after which the audio recordings were deleted. For richness and nuance, the analysis was conducted on the Romanian transcripts. Quotes used in different outputs were translated into English by myself.

All fieldwork documents that is the instructions given to participants in order to produce the visuals (section 4) and the interview outline (section 5, except the summary section) were translated into English using Open AI's ChatGBT, the free version, accessed at <https://chatgpt.com/>, further edited to improve the translation.

4. VISUALS: PARTICIPANT INSTRUCTIONS

Participants were informed about the visual elements as shown below.

If you consented through the Consent Form, we will ask you, before the interview:

- 📷 To send us a few photographs of your home/rented property (for example, what you like, what you don't like);
- 📷 To sketch your housing history in the form of a path/road (for example, your parental home, your first independent home, and what you liked/didn't like about them, and why you moved).

The visual elements above are not mandatory, but they would help you reflect and help us understand your experiences better. During the interview, we will discuss your rental experiences in detail (including those based on the photos you send and the hand-drawn sketch).

Photographs of home

The following instructions were further offered for the photographs.

Landlords	Tenants
We would greatly appreciate if you could send us photographs of the home you currently live in, as well as of the property you rent to tenants (possibly	We would greatly appreciate if you could send us photographs of the home you currently live in (possibly public/archive photos), showing the quality of the property and what makes it feel like a 'home.'

⁶ Genz, C., and Helbrecht, I. (2022). "Negotiations of Urban Ontological Security: The Impact of Housing Insecurity on Being-in-the-City." *Housing, Theory and Society*, 1-20.

⁷ Soaita, A. M., and McKee, K. (2021). "Researching home's tangible and intangible materialities by photo-elicitation." *Housing, Theory and Society*, 38(3), 279-299.

⁸ Neumark, D. (2013). "Drawn to Beauty: The Practice of House-Beautification as Homemaking amongst the Forcibly Displaced." *Housing, Theory and Society*, 30(3), 237-261.

⁹ Stout, A., and Collins, D. (2024). "Picturing a home: a new perspective on home-making through photo-elicitation." *Housing, Theory and Society*, 41(3), 360-378.

¹⁰ Coleman, T., and Wiles, J. (2018). "Being With Objects of Meaning: Cherished Possessions and Opportunities to Maintain Aging in Place." *The Gerontologist*, 60(1), 41-49.

¹¹ Klitzing, S. W. (2004). "Women Living in a Homeless Shelter: Stress, Coping and Leisure." *Journal of Leisure Research*, 36(4), 483-512.

¹² Oter-Quintana, C., González-Gil, T., Martín-García, Á., and Alcolea-Cosín, M. T. (2017). "Photoelicitation: A Useful Tool to Investigate Management of the Vulnerability of Homeless Women." *Enfermería Clínica*, 27(5), 308-313.

public/archive photos), showing the quality of the property and what makes it feel like a 'home.'

My housing journey (hand-drawn sketch)

Building on the River of Life method, a visual representation of one's life in the form of a river,^{13 14 15 16} the following instructions were further offered for the drawings.

Dear [name],

Thank you so much for agreeing to draw your housing history/journey on paper. Please feel free to draw it in any form you prefer. However, to make it easier for you, we offer some suggestions and examples.

In principle, you can draw your housing journey as a road representing your path from one home to another. A simpler representation can be made in the form of a list where each home you lived in is represented briefly as a simple circle/dot. Alternatively, if you'd like to practice your drawing skills, it can be represented as:

- A façade sketch (for example, a simple image of a house or apartment building);
- An image of the street (for example, neighbouring buildings, trees, buses);
- A floor plan sketch (room layout).

It is very helpful to add explanatory text, such as the period you lived in each (or your age, in years), the location, the number of rooms, and briefly mention (even with just one word) what was most important to you. Please give each home a symbolic name, a "nickname" (for example, I named my home on the 9th floor "my nest in the sky"). If you wish, you can also introduce the idea of the future ("the dream house").

You can also use emotional symbols (such as a smiling or sad face, or sun or rain). If you have multiple properties (for example, properties that you rent out), you can draw them on parallel paths. The sketch doesn't have to be "beautiful"; it should represent your personal journey. If you find it "ugly," don't throw it away—it's still useful to us, no matter how it looks!

Before you start drawing, make a plan:

- **Reflect:** How many homes have I lived in total? What were the reasons for moving? What stage of my life do they represent? What period do I want to represent? (For example, the last 10 years, 20 years, or my entire life).
- **Plan:** Start drawing the path; mark the timeline in terms of age or period; give a name/nickname to each home; mark key events, emotions, or people; add explanatory notes.
- **Contextualise:** Did any event happen in the world, locally, regionally, or globally that influenced my journey? Simply mark such an event with a keyword.
- **Evaluate:** Am I satisfied with the representation I've made? If you wish, you can copy or redraw it on a clean sheet of paper, because now you know exactly what you want to represent.

On the next page, I present a few examples. Since you will be sharing your route and story with me during the interview, as a gesture of reciprocity, one of the examples shown is my own route.

Thank you,

¹³ Denov, M., and Shevell, M. C. (2021). "An arts-based approach with youth born of genocidal rape in Rwanda: The river of life as an autobiographical mapping tool." *Global Studies of Childhood*, 11(1), 21-39.

¹⁴ Iantaffi, A. (2011). "Travelling along 'rivers of experience': personal construct psychology and visual metaphors in research", in P. Reavey, (ed.), *Visual Methods in Psychology: Using and Interpreting Images in Qualitative Research*. London: Routledge.

¹⁵ Moussa, Z. (2009). "Tips for trainers: rivers of life." *PLA 60*(G02828), 8.

¹⁶ Soaita, A. M. (2024). "The "River of Life": Researching Migration Trajectories Through Elicitation Based on Participants' Drawings", in SAGE, (ed.), *SAGE Research Methods: Doing Research Online, Cases*. SAGE.

Figure 1 My housing history in the form of a list with circles

Figure 2 My Housing history in the form of a road and an image of the area

Drawn by Adriana Soaita

Figure 3 My housing history in the form of a list and the floor plan of the home

Drawn by a participant, anonymized by Adriana Soaita. Shown with participant's permission.

Figure 4 My housing history in the form of a road and the façade of the home

Drawn by a participant, anonymized by Adriana Soaita. Shown with participant's permission.

5. INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Summary

The development of the interview questions benefited from my involvement in prior qualitative research projects with the UK as a case study,^{17 18 19 20 21 22 23} as well as large literature syntheses of the qualitative literature focusing on rented housing across the Anglo-Saxon countries,²⁴ OECD countries,²⁵ and the Majority World.²⁶ It also benefited from my knowledge as an expert in Romanian housing^{27 28 29 30 31 32 33} As is common, the interview questions were refined following piloting with two academic colleagues and six friends (two homeowners, two tenants, two landlords).

The interview was structured into three parts. Part 1, on visual elicitation, was led by the participants themselves as they followed their housing history and commented on the photos they had sent. Part 2 was guided by questions that closely followed the process of renting as experienced by the participants (from reasons for renting, finding a tenancy/tenant, property quality, management practices, affordability, to future plans). Finally, Part 3 inquired more broadly about how the rental system works in Romania and probed for solutions for improvement, many of which were inspired by the broader literature.

¹⁷ McKee, K., Moore, T., Soaita, A. M., and Crawford, J. (2017). "Generation Rent and the fallacy of choice." *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(2), 318-333.

¹⁸ McKee, K., Soaita, A. M., and Hoolachan, J. (2020). "'Generation rent' and the emotions of private renting: self-worth, status and insecurity amongst low-income renters." *Housing Studies*, 35(8), 1468-1487.

¹⁹ Soaita, A. M., Searle, B. A., McKee, K., and Moore, T. (2016). "Becoming a landlord: property-based welfare and vulnerability in the private rental market in Great Britain." *Housing Studies*, 32(5), 613-637.

²⁰ Soaita, A. M., and McKee, K. (2019). "Assembling a 'kind of' home in the UK private renting sector." *Geoforum*, 103(July), 148-157.

²¹ Soaita, A. M., and Searle, B. A. (2018). "Homeownership-based welfare? Wealth options for owner-occupiers and tenants in Britain", in B. A. Searle, (ed.), *Generational Interdependencies: The Social Implications for Welfare*. Vernon Press, pp. 236-257.

²² Soaita, A. M. (2022). "Researching tenant activism by using an uncommon method: the online written interview", in SAGE, (ed.), *SAGE Research Methods: Doing Research Online, Cases*. SAGE, <https://methods.sagepub.com/case/researching-tenant-activism-uncommon-method-online-written-interview>

²³ Soaita, A. M., and McKee, K. (2021). "Researching home's tangible and intangible materialities by photo-elicitation " *Housing, Theory and Society*, 38(3), 279-299.

²⁴ Soaita, A. M., Munro, M., and McKee, K. (2020). *Private renters' housing experiences in lightly regulated markets: a review of qualitative research*. University of Glasgow, CaCHE, Glasgow.

²⁵ Soaita, A. M., Simcock, T., and McKee, K. (2022). *Housing challenges faced by low-income and other vulnerable privately renting households: an evidence review*. University of Glasgow, CaCHE, Glasgow.

²⁶ Soaita, A. M. (2025). "Structures of feeling in the affective economies of renting in the Majority World: An interpretative synthesis of the academic literature." *Geoforum*, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0016718525000685>

²⁷ Soaita, A. M., and Dewilde, C. (2019). "A critical-realist view of housing quality within the post-communist EU states: progressing towards a middle-range explanation." *Housing, Theory and Society*, 36(1), 44-75.

²⁸ Soaita, A. M. (2017). "The changing nature of outright home ownership in Romania: housing wealth and housing inequality ", in C. Dewilde and R. Ronald, (eds.), *Housing Wealth and Welfare*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp. 236-257.

²⁹ Soaita, A. M. (2015). "The meaning of home in Romania: views from urban owner-occupiers." *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 30(1), 69-85.

³⁰ Soaita, A. M. (2014). "Overcrowding and 'under-occupancy' in Romania: a case study of housing inequality." *Environment and Planning A*, 46(1), 203 – 221.

³¹ Soaita, A. M. (2013). "Romanian suburban housing: home improvement through owner-building." *Urban Studies*, 50(10), 2084-2101.

³² Soaita, A. M. (2012). "Strategies for in-situ home improvement in Romanian large housing estates." *Housing Studies*, 27(7), 1008-1030.

³³ Soaita, A. M. (2010). *Unregulated Housing Privatism: A Comparative Analysis of the Nature and Extent of Housing Problems and Resident Responses in Two Forms of Romanian Urban Housing*, PhD, King's College London, London.

The framework proposed was therefore built in a mixed inductive/deductive approach, which is appropriate for pioneering research on a social world that has so far been overlooked.

Warming-up

Warming up: Hello, [name], thank you [etc.]. A brief reiteration of the terms of consent given in the signed Consent Form. Do you have any questions about this?
About the interview: The interview has three parts (briefly explain: housing journey; current home; system). You can skip any question you prefer not to answer. Is there anything you would like to ask me at this point?
Some personal data (for participants who did not complete the questionnaire): First, I would like to ask a few short questions, questionnaire-style:
✚ Age
✚ Town
✚ In your current home: number of rooms and number of people
✚ Education: last school completed
✚ Employment: PT/FT/Retired/Student, etc.
✚ How many years have you been renting? How many homes? Where (number of rooms and number of people for each)?
Recording: Can I now start recording our conversation? You will be asked to agree by clicking a button. Thank you.

Visual elicitation (part 1)

Housing history (in-depth visual elicitation)

Brief explanation: I would like to understand your housing journey, including what you liked or didn't like along the way. Could you briefly tell me about the homes you've lived in—one by one, but briefly—and the circumstances of your move(s)? I will follow the drawing you made.
✚ But first, tell me: how was it for you to do this very [informative/beautiful, etc.] drawing? Probe: Did it take a long time, several attempts, etc.?
✚ While the participant leads this in-depth discussion, the drawings provide the researcher with an excellent summary and help formulate specific prompts on missing information (timeline, nicknames, occupancy) or participant-specific information (circumstances) or details (e.g. "you drew [xx] there, what do they represent?").
✚ If the participant has not provided a housing-journey visual, the discussion proceeds by asking about the places the participant lived in chronological order.
Comfort pause: Would you like a brief pause before moving on to discuss the photos you sent?

Photos of home (brief discussion)

Could you please take me briefly through the photos you sent and tell me what they mean to you? Possible probes:
✚ What do you like and what do you dislike the most?
✚ Do you feel at home here? Probe: What makes you feel at home here?
✚ If some rooms are missing, ask why.
✚ If participants point to certain objects/features, ask why they are significant.
✚ If you observe dangers/hazards, ask for clarification.
For landlords: if they sent photos of both their own home and their rented property/ies, discuss the former first, followed by the latter (marked by a pause, e.g. drink water, make a joke, etc.). Ask how they think the two compare in terms of features, quality, and homeliness.

The rented property/home (part 2)

Let's now talk about your renting experience and the home you are renting. [Note: As certain aspects may have already been discussed in the housing history/journey or photos, make sure you do not repeat them but briefly summarise from your notes].

Landlords	Tenants
<p>Reasons/circumstances: Can I first ask what reasons and under what circumstances you decided to rent this property/properties? (Probe on: <i>Inheritance, employment, was this your previous home, thought of a home for children, investment...</i> Does any of this apply to you?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ How did you finance the purchase? Could you tell me how much it cost? How easy/difficult was it to find? How many other homes did you view before buying it? ✚ How does it compare to the home you are living in? (Similar, larger/smaller, better/worse location) 	<p>Reasons/circumstances: But let's start with the reasons why you decided to rent, what would they be? (Probe on: <i>Employment circumstances, family situation, income, preferences, lack of access to other homes, location, affordability...</i> Does any of this apply to you?)</p>
<p>Quality: Would you say that, from a quality perspective, it is a well-maintained home (have you had to make repairs?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Have you done any renovations? ✚ And what about the furniture? ✚ What about the location? 	<p>Quality: To what extent does your current home meet your needs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ From a quality perspective, is it a well-maintained home? ✚ Does the location meet your needs? ✚ How does it compare to your previous home in terms of quality?
<p>Finding a tenant: How easy or difficult was it to find tenants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Please describe that delicate moment of the first meeting: what do you discuss, how do you behave, who is present... ✚ How do you decide whether or not to trust that tenant? ✚ And the tenant, how do you think they build trust in you? (What do you think are your strengths, so to speak?) ✚ Do you have preferences for a certain type of tenant? (Probe: with/without children, pets, age or gender, other ethnicities, foreign citizens?) Why? ✚ How many viewing do you commonly have before deciding to whom to rent? 	<p>Finding a tenancy: How easy or difficult was it to find it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ How many other homes did you view before deciding? ✚ Please describe that delicate moment of the first meeting: what did you discuss, how did you behave, who was present (and why?)... ✚ How do you decide whether or not to trust the landlord? (The condition of the home, the asking price, or even their clothing, way of speaking?) ✚ And the landlord, how do you think they decide whether or not to trust you? (What do you think are your strengths, so to speak?) ✚ Do you have preferences for a certain type of landlord? (Education, job, age, gender, family?) ✚ Have you ever felt negatively discriminated against by landlords/real estate agents during the rental process? (For having children, pets...) If yes, could you tell me about the circumstances?
<p>Letting agents: Have you used the services of agencies/agents? Why yes/no?</p>	<p>Letting agents: Have you used the services of agencies/agents? Why yes/no?</p>
<p>The rent: Could you tell me how much the rent is?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ How do you determine the rent amount? (quality/location; above/below average) Do you calculate the net profit? ✚ Do you accept negotiations? 	<p>The rent: Could you tell me how much the rent is?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ May I ask what your monthly net income is or alterantivly, approximately how much is your rent reported to income as a percentage?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Do you usually increase it during the rental period? ✚ Would you like your tenant to stay in your property for a longer time? Why yes/no? Probe: Have you ever evicted a tenant? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Is it easy for you to afford it, or do you have to give up other things to afford it? (trips, socializing with friends) ✚ Have you had it increased during the rental period?
<p>Utilities costs: How do you handle utility payments? (probe: electricity, gas, TV, internet, etc)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ On whose name are the contracts, and how are costs paid? If yes: Would you have preferred it to be in your name? ✚ Do you find the calculation of utility costs transparent? 	<p>Utilities costs: Would you say that the utility costs are significant or not quite? (probe: electricity, gas, TV, internet, etc)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Is the utility contract in the landlord's name? If yes: Would you have preferred it to be in your name? ✚ Is the calculation of costs transparent?
<p>Social distance/proximity: Do you happen to know why your tenant is renting? (they can't afford to buy; they still don't know what they want; they don't have a stable job)</p>	<p>Safety/security/emotions: Do you feel safe in this home?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Earthquake? The possibility that the landlord might ask you to move out? Has anyone ever asked you to leave the home? ✚ Would you like to stay in this property for a long time? Why yes/no?
	<p>The ideal/future situation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ How does living in the private rental sector make you feel? For example, do you feel happy, content, comfortable, proud or rather disappointed, embarrassed, frustrated, stressed, or angry? (Why do you feel this way?) ✚ What would your ideal living situation be for now? [This]: Who or what would help you achieve your ideal? (luck, job, income, family); [Different]: Why haven't you been able to achieve your ideal? (job, income, family) What would your ideal living situation be for the future, say in 10 years? ✚ In the future, would you like to buy? Who or what do you think would help you achieve your ideal? (income, your family, being in a relationship)
<p>To conclude this part:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Would you say that your rental experience has been positive or negative? Why? ✚ Do you plan to rent this property for a long time from now on? Why yes/no? ✚ If yes: Do you see this activity as a business, a kind of insurance, or a secondary activity? 	<p>To conclude this part:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Would you say that your living experience in the private sector has been positive or negative? Why? ✚ How would you say your living experience compares to that of your close friends? Are they similar or different? Perhaps you're thinking of 2-3 close friends. [Probe on the why is similar/different: family support, life events, income, family size, health condition)
<p>Comfort pause: Would you like a brief pause before we move on to discuss the renting system in Romania more generally?</p>	

The private renting system (part 3)

<p>General information/knowledge: What sources of information do you have regarding how the market works?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Are you familiar with the current legislation?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Do you read press articles, Facebook groups, or real estate pages?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Do you talk to friends who rent like you?

Public discourse: How would you say the private rental sector in Romania is described in the public domain from the perspective of the tenant? (Probe: accepted, stigmatized, risky). And from the perspective of the landlord? (Probe: a good/risky way to invest?)	
Future trends: What do you think the future trends are regarding the private rental sector?	
Policy suggestions:	
Landlords	Tenants
<p>Do you have any suggestions on how landlords could be protected against late rent payments or property damage? Probes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Quick court system; Higher deposit; The right to ask the tenant for references before renting; Deduction of expenses from income taxes in case of property damage; Government guarantee? <p>Do you have any suggestions on how tenants could be protected against unjustified eviction, rent increases, or other forms of abuse?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Quick court system; Ban on evictions during winter months; Limiting the legal reasons for which a tenant can be evicted? 	<p>Do you have any suggestions on how tenants could be protected against unjustified eviction, rent increases, or other forms of abuse?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Quick court system; Ban on evictions during winter months; Limiting the legal reasons for which a tenant can be evicted? <p>Do you have any suggestions on how landlords could be protected against late rent payments or property damage? Probes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Quick court system; Higher deposit; The right to ask the tenant for references before renting; Deduction of expenses from income taxes in case of property damage; Government guarantee?
Ending the recording: Would you like to mention any other aspects that I may have overlooked? If not, I will now switch off the recording.	

Debriefing

For those who did not complete the questionnaire: I still have two more brief questionnaire-type questions.
<p>First one, is about the economic situation. Would you describe the total household income as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Allowed saving/investing substantial amounts ✚ Allowed saving/investing minor amounts ✚ Was sufficient, but did not allow for savings/investments ✚ Was not sufficient, I used savings made previously ✚ Was not sufficient, I used loans or support from family/others
<p>In the coming year, do you expect your household's financial situation to be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Better than now ✚ The same as now ✚ Worse than now ✚ I can't say
Debriefing: How did you find the questions? Thank you so much for sharing your experiences and for the insights you gave us, etc.

6. RESULTING DATA

Interviews: The visual-elicitation interviews were conducted between April 2023 and February 2024, involving 20 tenants, 15 landlords, and 3 individuals who were tenants in one place and landlords in another (total 38). Of these, 13 were sourced through questionnaire self-referrals, and 25 through further advertising in the same Facebook groups. Interviews lasted an average of 91 minutes (minimum 53 minutes; maximum 204 minutes).

Housing history/journey drawings: Two participants declined to send a drawing (they felt drawing was too challenging for them); most sent one, while seven sent a series of between 2 and 5. In total, 51 photographed handmade and computerised drawings were received from 36 participants.

Photos of home/rented property: One participant declined to send photos. In total, 514 photos were received from 37 participants (minimum 3; median 13; maximum 67).